

Amperometric Studies on the Composition of Rare Earths Isopolytungstates—Samarium Polytungstate-Part I

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Amperometric titrations were performed between the various alkali tungstates and $\text{Sm}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ solution. The well defined breaks in titration curve indicate the formation and precipitation of normal, para and tri-tungstates of Samarium at pH ranges (6.0-7.0), (5.0-6.0) and (4.6-5.0) respectively.

It is well known that the outstanding characteristics of tungstates is their strong tendency to form condensed complex ions in solution as revealed by the observations of Jander and Jahr¹; from these polytungstates crystallize, depending on H^+ ion concentration which plays an important role in the aggregation process. The existence of polytungstates is usually attributed to combination with the corresponding acids as if these were separate chemical individuals. This led the previous workers to believe that similar salts of heavy metals might be precipitated as a result of metathesis². Britton and German³ however, contended that corresponding salts of heavy metals could not be obtained with different alkali tungstates. Kuan Puan *et al.*⁴ and Freedman⁵ have reported the existence of $\text{W}_2\text{O}_7^{4-}$, $\text{W}_3\text{O}_{11}^{4-}$, $\text{HW}_6\text{O}_{21}^{3-}$, $\text{H}_2\text{W}_6\text{O}_{21}^{4-}$ and $\text{H}_3\text{W}_6\text{O}_{21}^{3-}$ whereas Sasaki⁶ inferred that $\text{HW}_6\text{O}_{21}^{3-}$ is the main polyanion formed. Kepert⁷ in a recent review has also argued in favour of the latter works. However, there is a great divergence in the views of previous workers regarding the formation of various polyanions. Admittedly the polymerisation of tungstate ion in acidic media is still not completely understood.

There is probably no reference in literature regarding the electrometric investigation on the reaction between $\text{Sm}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ and Na_2WO_4 at different pH levels, although some electrometric references^{8,9} on the formation and precipitation of normal Samarium tungstate are available in literature. It has, therefore, been considered worthwhile to investigate precisely the compositions of Samarium iso-polytungstates obtained by the interaction of $\text{Sm}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ and alkali tungstate at different pH ranges by amperometric technique of analysis and the results are incorporated in the present paper.

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EXPERIMENTAL

Anal. R. (B. D. H) $\text{Sm}(\text{NO}_3)_3$, Na_2WO_4 , LiCl , gelatine were used. Air free conductivity water was used for the preparation and subsequent dilutions of the solutions.

A manual polarograph with a spot galvanometer was used for polarographic and amperometric work. A dropping mercury electrode having the following characteristics, $m^2/3t^{1/2} = 4.58 \text{ mg}^2/\text{sec}^{-1/2}$, droptime $t = 3.64$ secs. at -1.0 volts, (vs. S.C.E.)—was used in conjunction with a S.C.E. connected to the cell by a low resistance salt bridge. Polarographic behaviour of 1 mM Sm^{2+} was studied in 0.1 M LiCl as supporting electrolyte. All the amperometric titrations were carried out at an applied potential of -1.7 v (vs. S.C.E.) in presence of 0.1 M LiCl as supporting electrolyte and 0.005% gelatine as a maximum suppressor. The procedure adopted is same as described earlier¹⁰.

The various alkali tungstate solutions were prepared by addition of requisite quantities of HCl on standard normal sodium tungstate solution at 100° . A series of amperometric titrations were then performed between $\text{Sm}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ and each of the different alkali tungstate solutions at various concentrations in aqueous and in the presence of 20% ethanol also. The results of the various titrations are summarised in Table I. Only four figures have been given for the sake of brevity.

FIG. I

FIG. II

DISCUSSION

Our investigations have shown that the formation of various polytungstates corresponds to the different stages, in the anomalous neutralization of Na tungstate by different acids, as indicated by the changes in H^+ ion concentrations. This is clear from Fig. I. We have, therefore, considered that any interaction of alkali tungstate and metal salt in solution would be largely governed by H^+ ion concentration that would be set up

by the reactants and these consequently would have pronounced effect on the composition of the precipitates. A series of reactions between Samarium nitrate and each of the alkali tungstates have been thus studied by electrometric techniques at different pH ranges.

TABLE I
Summary of results of amperometric titrations

Sm (NO ₃) ₃	Concentrations		Ratio	Equivalence points (ml)		
	Na ₂ WO ₄			Calculated (ml)	Observed (ml)	
					Aq. (Normal Tungstate)	Aquo-ethanolic Fig. II.
M/40	M/200		1:5	2.66	2.60	2.65
M/250	M/1000		1:4	3.33	3.40	3.40
M/100	M/500		1:5	2.66	2.70	2.70
M/1280	M/160		8:1	3.75	3.70	3.70
M/2400	M/320		8:1	4.00	3.95	3.95
	(Na ₂ O.2.33WO ₃)			(Paratungstate)		Fig. III
M/320	M/1631		1:5.1	2.63	2.55	2.55
M/40	M/116.5		1:2.91	4.57	4.50	4.55
M/160	M/652.4		1:4.07	3.28	3.50	2.45
	(Na ₂ O.3WO ₃)			(Tri tungstate)		Fig. IV.
M/40	M/150		1:3.8	3.55	3.35	3.35
M/40	M/160		1:4	3.33	3.10	3.10
M/40	M/120		1:3	4.44	4.40	4.45

Normal tungstate titrations: (Fig. 3) Amperometric titrations were carried out by using different concentrations of Sm(NO₃)₃ and Na₂WO₄ solutions at -1.7v (vs. S.C.E.) at which Sm⁺⁺⁺ ion gives a wave while WO₄²⁻ ion does not produce any wave. The plots drawn between diffusion current and the volume of titrant added, indicate well defined breaks at the point of intersection of two linear portions of the curves, at a stage where the molecular ratio of the reacting species Sm: W=2:3 suggesting the formation of normal Samarium tungstate with the composition Sm₂O₃.3WO₃ at pH range (6.0-7.0) according to following reaction equilibria:

Di and para tungstate titrations: (Fig. 4) Sodium di and para tungstate solutions were prepared by adding requisite amounts of HCl to normal Sodium tungstate solution at 100°. Amperometric titration were performed between Sm(NO₃)₃, di and para tungstate solutions respectively.

After examining the curves in both systems, it was found that the para tungstate ion is only predominant one at pH range (5.0-5.5-6.0). The well defined break obtained indicate the formation and precipitation of Samarium para tungstate Sm₂O₃.7WO₃.

Tri tungstate titrations: (Fig. 4) Solution of Sodium tri tungstate was prepared by addition of requisite amount of HCl to Na_2WO_4 solution at 100° which was titrated amperometrically with $\text{Sm}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ solutions.

FIG. III

FIG. IV

The sharp break in the titrations curves confirmed the formation of Samarium tritungstate $\text{Sm}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 9\text{WO}_3$ at pH range (4.0-5.0) as it is clear from following equation:

No evidence for formation of tetratingstate of Samarium was obtained.

Thus the present investigation confirms the formation and precipitation of normal, para and tritungstates of Samarium having different compositions at different pH ranges.

The above results have been substantiated by conductometric titrations with the same solutions and analytical methods also.

These titrations were found to be accurate and reproducible over a wide range of concentration of Sm^{3+} or WO_4^{2-} ion. The precipitate is a quantitative one in case of normal compounds and can be utilised for the determination of Sm or W to an accuracy of 0.5 to 1.0% in 10^{-4}M concentration of the reactants used.

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